

USE OF MODERN TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CONDUCT OF PHYSICS LABORATORY WORKS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the methodology of using modern teaching technologies in conducting laboratory work in secondary schools.*

Key words: *laboratory work, independent education, physical quantities, interactive teaching tools, electronic learning tools, scientific and technical information.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПРИ ПРОВЕДЕНИИ ЛАБОРАТОРНЫХ РАБОТ ПО ФИЗИКЕ В ОБЩИХ СРЕДНИХ ШКОЛАХ

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена информация о методике использования современных технологий обучения при проведении лабораторных работ в общеобразовательных школах.*

Ключевые слова: *лабораторная работа, самостоятельное обучение, физические величины, интерактивные средства обучения, электронные средства обучения, научно-техническая информация.*

Today, the urgent task of world education is to improve general education, as well as professional education. To solve the above-mentioned task, the goals and results of education are revised, the content of education is changed, and the term "practical competence" is increasingly used. Due to the reforms in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the term "practical competence" began to be used.

Despite the constant growth of publications devoted to the development of a competency-based approach in education, this problem in the field of teaching physics has not been sufficiently studied. Laboratory work is of great importance in the development of students' scientific competences. The use of modern pedagogical technologies in conducting laboratory work creates a basis for making the lesson process more interesting and understandable.

The structure of laboratory work consists of the teacher's management and the student's independent work. In the existing guidelines for the performance of routine laboratory work, the given descriptions have a theoretical part, which mainly describes the theoretical information necessary for the performance of the work. Through this information, students can briefly prepare for work from a theoretical point of view.

One of the most important requirements for modern laboratory classes is to increase the effectiveness of the effective connection of educational methods and innovative technologies. So what is innovation? How are innovative pedagogical and information technologies used? The word innovation is derived from the English word "innovation", which means creating something new. The innovative activity of the teacher is considered as a creative process, a result of creative activity.

The stages of innovative activity are as follows:

- ✓ Prepared methodological recommendations will be clearly copied.
- ✓ Some devices and methodical methods are included in the existing system.

- ✓ The content, methods and form of implementing the idea will be fully developed.
- ✓ A unique concept and methodology of teaching and upbringing will be created.

Stages of the innovation process:

- ✓ the stage of the birth of a new idea or the emergence of a new concept, it is also called discovery;
- ✓ the stage of inventing, creating new things;
- ✓ the stage of being able to apply the created innovation in practice;
- ✓ the stage of spreading the innovation, its wide application;
- ✓ the stage of dominance of innovation in a certain field, at this stage the innovation loses its novelty, its effective alternative appears;
- ✓ the stage of reducing the scope of application of the innovation by replacement based on a new alternative.

Innovative technologies, the pedagogical process and the introduction of innovations and changes in the activity of the teacher and student, and mainly interactive methods are fully used in its implementation. Interactive methods are called collective thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of the educational content. Interactive is a Latin word, "inter" means mutually active, that is, it is an active relationship, perception, full understanding between the teacher and the student.

In the process of increasing and accumulating scientific and scientific-technical information, it will be very difficult to achieve the goals aimed at improving teaching. For this reason, it will be necessary to make certain changes to the principles of organizing the teaching process, including improving the presentation of educational materials. In this case, the introduction of modern information technologies into the educational process and their use is considered one of the most effective ways to achieve the goal.

Currently, the development and wide application of information and communication technologies is a global trend of world development. New technologies are developing day by day, and in the period of rapid development of the informatization process in the country, special attention is being paid to the organization of information resources in the field of education. Scientific research on the introduction of modern information technologies into the educational system has been covered in a number of research works.

Any science generalizes some concepts of existence and studies them in connection with each other. For example, physics studies events and phenomena in nature, the conditions of their origin, and their use in human life. Various methods and techniques are used in teaching physics. In physics, the basis of knowledge is the practical examination of theoretical knowledge and mastered knowledge. In both cases, when mastering the material, a certain level of information is brought to the minds of students.

The main principle of the intellectual system is that a person's logical way of thinking is used to solve a problem. When searching for solutions to complex problems, a person is based on knowledge of certain laws. It uses mathematical theorems or rules from practice, breaks down complex problems into simpler ones, and applies other methods.

In general, the main task of an intellectual system is to implement the accumulated knowledge and search for optimal ways to solve complex problems using it and find a solution.

Hardware required to create such virtual systems consists of:

- cheap, simple, compact computers with multimedia tools;
- software support for "everywhere" applications;
- miniature transceivers (transceivers) for communication of computers with each other and with the network;
- distributed broadband communication channels and networks.

Many of the prerequisites for creating the specified constructors and their simplest representations are already in place, but there are also problems. The most important of these is to ensure data privacy and intellectual property rights so that all of our personal lives do not become public property.

Currently, in the field of education, a lot of attention is paid to the automation of teaching, because the use of modern teaching technologies in the course of the lesson gives great positive results. The following can be included in the program of automation of education (informatization) or the use of information technologies:

- a) to ensure the leading link of informatization at all levels of the educational system;
- b) design and creation (monitoring) of the development of informatization in education in all areas, resource center system;
- c) creation of normative bases in the field of information (coordination, methods, scientific-methodical associations, etc.);
- g) creation of technical support - computers, other information technology devices (from a camera to a microscope), necessary materials for their service;
- d) telecommunication networks (over the air, earth satellites and other communication channels);
- e) supply resources (software, information sets on the Internet, references, etc.).

The use of information technology and its implementation in a certain field includes a number of tasks. Below we will talk about the objects of informed activity.

Such objects include numbers (results of measurements and modeling), texts, statistical and dynamic representations of visual information, pictures, drawings and animations, sound images (recorded voice, music, etc.).

Serious changes are taking place in the field of knowledge acquisition and education, and information in this field is of great interest to many. So, acquiring the most necessary knowledge in a field quickly and in a short time, that is, relations in the knowledge market have changed significantly.

In this regard, the creation of pedagogical program tools and their use in the course of the lesson will fundamentally change the quality of learning. Therefore, there is a need to automate all the processes, starting from the explanation of the educational material in the lesson to the assignment of tasks at home. What technical equipment is used to create pedagogical program tools? Pedagogical software tools can be conditionally divided into three main groups: hardware software tools, control software tools, and teaching improvement software tools.

The scientific analysis of determining the place of laboratory training in the continuous education system shows that the physpracticum in higher education requires a wider, deeper, improved study.

Taking into account the need to improve the continuous education system in our republic, to raise it to the level of world education standards, as well as other types of lessons, the content

of physpraktikum (laboratory training), the latest achievements in the field, it is necessary to improve and differentiate teaching methods using modern teaching technologies.

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